

AMONG DENTISTS IN LAHORE A POPULAR METHOD OF FIELD ISOLATION: A RESEARCH STUDY CONDUCTED ON RUBBER DAM

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Abstract:

Objective: To discover the occurrence of rubber dam practice amid medical students, internship students, Dentists and what are the problems do they face if they use it regularly.

Method: A survey conducted from October 2016 to January 2017 using non-probability expediency case. The opinion poll carefully planned that had questions used in parallel researches in the precedent. Questionnaires distributed among Medical Dental Students, Internees and dentists doing practice in different teaching hospitals in Lahore and Doctors working common dental jobs. SPSS software version 20 used to get Information from opinion poll.

Results: Among the respondents, a very positive reply of 81% showed that the research revealed that a very high percentage of 76% of Medical Students, interneers and Dental Doctors working in Lahore teaching Hospitals paid no attention to rubber dam placement in their routine job. 89% of Doctors who were not interested in using it because they thought it as a time wasting, while others 66% found it heavy due to which it was very hard to put it. Few other reasons due to which people shun to use rubber dam are that 50% participants thinks the regular tearing pages and patient's fright approach towards rubber dam. **Conclusion:** This research concludes using rubber dam is disliked process for separation of functioning position between Medical Students, interneers and Dental Doctors working in Lahore.

Keywords: Rubber dam, dentists, foreign bodies.

INTRODUCTION:

Functioning dentists' measures use a massive quantity of common dentists' cure time and need to take away such dental measures in arid circumstances are accepted and are well noted. Many processes of working ground separation seen to shun infectivity from dribble and few more verbal fluids. One choice that Dentists comprise is that assimilation by means of cotton rolls, gauze, withdrawal sting, migration during dribble ejectors and powerful influence suction. Rubber band measured to be the finest separation technique, for the very first time it invented by Dr. Sanford Christie Barnum in 1864. It is composed of very stretchable latex that acts as a wall when used to teeth and presents page of 6x6 inches of following teeth and 5x5 inches for front teeth. It found in different colors and of different width.

Rubber dam separation measured compulsory in modern dental works as patient in healing, at the same stage, mostly healing processes are in supine place. At this time patient probably swallow a very tiny tool, for example pronunciation is unintentionally slip from Dentists hand. Ones who do not use rubber dam have exposed to pressurize the option of root canal irrigation resolution that might have bad impact in healing result because when they use sodium hypochlorite it has such an awful flavor that you can't bear it without rubber dam. Furthermore, when patients swallow the unfamiliar swallowing things for example exclusion of unsuccessful mixture, alongside chip china wear, this also saw in occasions when rubber dam separation did not used. Although the majority of distant things go by during alimentary duct calmly, except a very few develop into stuck, frequently to the throat it has serious threat. Through achievement of an effective dentistry process, a presence of dentist is most susceptible to bond irritated infectivity during the patient's verbal fluid say dribble, provocative exudates. The probable doubt of irritated infectivity among Dentists and the patients might be decreased if cannot remove totally by using rubber dam isolation in place of few other methods for field separation.

As we know about rubber dam isolation since 150 years with all the profit and ease of use, yet it could not increase the reputation all over the world for efficient separation method 6-8. Similar to several other nations, exercise of rubber dam is barely common amongst Dentists and dental students in Pakistan. According to our information, duo researches are on hand that offer various information concerning the dentists approach towards rubber dam

assignment; dentists working in northern side of the state are connect to it.

Lahore is second the largest city of Pakistan that has supplementary 12 dental institutes purpose to provide countless dental students, interneers, postgraduate students and teachers. Statistics to disclose practice and attitudes of Dentists functioning or the dental students in the metropolitan hardly exists. Single research gives information about the information and attitude of dental students about practicing rubber dam, but in this research study clue did not gave. Answer to this research problem may give us fair idea about ignoring of disclose the causes of necessary separation process .Benefit of the research was to decide the occurrence of rubber dam usage between Medical students, interneers and dentists and what are the problems do they face while using this in daily basis.

METHODOLOGY:

The opinion poll survey was conducted between the medical students' interneers and medical Teachers of numerous Dental institutions present in Lahore. A group of research students have shaped the questions in opinion poll through self and look. To test the consistency of opinion poll Cronbach's alpha test with value 0.8 was used .The end Likert's scale review type with close-ended query that have respondents' preference of "Yes" and "No" has been actually dispersed amongst medical student, Interneers and teachers concerned in broad dental procedures during a designated central individual in every dental institution. Designated central individual too liable for consultation the participants on reason of research, to tackle someone feel uncertainty in the survey and to gather the filling of review form to single individual expediency in a week following sharing. As for privacy and secrecy of individuals, the person's name, organization or any private information was not gathered from them. Survey was done through October 2016 to January 2017 by means of non-probability expediency sampling method. The opinion poll consisted of two parts, the primary for demographic and other part limited to easy interrogation on the exercise or non exercise of rubber dam as a regular medical practice in working. Non exercise individuals of rubber dam separation were asked to give problems that they face while practicing this.

Statistics as of the finished survey were noted by means of SPSS for Windows version 20, and was displayed as statistics and percentages. Pearson Chi square test was practically used to make sure the connection of rubber dam exercise between groups.

RESULTS:

The respondents in survey respond quite well 81% as out of 250 questionnaire forms dispersed, 202 fill questionnaires were obtained. Survey questions were easy to answer; therefore all forms were totally filled with no rejection of a single form. Individuals in the study were composed of 80 last year medical students, 73 House officers and 49 common Dentists (Table 1). When they got the responses it was found that just 23.8% of the individuals used rubber dam in their Medical purposes (Table 2).

Left over 76% individuals did not use rubber dam due to unknown reasons regardless of the reality that most of they thought it as an efficient means for separation of operating ground and proves to be an improved oral secretions control in contrast to fiber rolls. An entirety 89% who did not use this procedure they thought it as waste of time, other 66% idea was that it was very hard to put it. Few other reasons because of which 50% of individuals shun the practice of rubber dam as common tearing of the page and patient's dread or abhor attitude about putting of rubber dam (Table 3).

Table 1. Feature of Individuals from dental Institutions in Lahore

Variables	Frequency (%)
Last Year Students	80 (40)
House Officers	73 (36)
Dental Practitioners	49 (24)
Total	202 (100)

Table 2. Occurrence of rubber dam exercise by Dental Students, house officers and Dentists in Lahore
Use of Rubber dam

	RD users N (%)	RD non-users N (%)	Totals N (%)	p-Value
Last Year Students	11 (5.5)	69 (34.5)	80 (40)	
House Officers	23 (11.4)	50 (24.6)	73 (36)	0.02*
Dental Practitioners	14 (6.9)	35 (17.1)	49 (24)	
Total	48 (23.8)	154 (76.2)	202 (100)	

*Significant at 95%

Table 3. Reasons for not using rubber dam by Dental students, house officers and Dentists in Lahore.

Variables	Yes N (%)	No N (%)	Total N (%)
I don't exercise RD due to subsequent reasons:	102 (66.2)	52 (33.8)	154 (100)
a. It is difficult to place	137 (89)	17 (11)	154 (100)
b. It is time consuming	18 (12)	136 (88)	154 (100)
c. It is ineffective			
d. Cotton rolls and gauze perform isolation as good as RD	51 (33)	103 (67)	154 (100)
e. It frequently tears	77 (50)	77 (50)	154 (100)
f. It leaks very often which causes failure of isolation	37 (24)	117 (76)	154 (100)
g. Patients feel fear or don't like i	89 (58)	65 (42)	154 (100)
h. I fear, patient may ingest the slipped RD clamp	49 (32)	105 (68)	154 (100)
i. I have insufficient training for its placemen	105 (68)	87 (56.5)	192 (100)
j. It increases the treatment cost	53 (34.4)	101 (65.6)	154 (100)

DISCUSSION:

Rubber dam is a well thought-out as the decisive technique for separation of operational ground in Dentist Medical Sciences. Regardless of their identified profit, exercise of rubber dam to take out functioning dentistry measures are not accepted technique of ground separation amongst Dentists all over the world. A thought to utilize rubber piece for separation of the working of dental place comes from 18th century however it seems unlikely that two Centuries later, bulk of universal dentists don't like usefulness of separation technique. Result in our research shows that just 23% of the individuals together with last year students, interneers and common dentists practice rubber dam. This proves that we are not different from other Dentists in the current world of none practicing of rubber dam. Our results showing similarity with a local research completed in Rawalpindi and Islamabad which shows that 28% dentists exercise rubber dam.

The Young Dental Students all over the world are taught on practicing regular use of rubber dam prior to healing [14-16]. This is unbelievable to note down that in 80 medical students that were involved in the research, out of these merely 11 regularly practically use rubber dam and others (n= 69) don't want to practice it. Only because of these results we are same with the Irish research study and Turkey research. In this respect, results of this study match the results of an Irish study [17] and a Turkish study [18]. An comprehensible motive for tirelessly avoiding that significant stride by medical dental students in our country might be to keep instance to achieve their compulsory medical share to craft them suitable to give away final exam. Teachers who teach under Graduate Dental students shall consider up to review the forced share to decrease difference among teaching in medical institutions and then its practical execution.

The occurrence of rubber dam practice by common working dentists all over the world reduces strongly once they qualify dental institution. Same case about no practice of rubber dam can be found between Pakistani. The facts in Table 2 demonstrates that barely 7% of responding common dentists thinks that effectiveness is not there in use of rubber of rubber dam in separation that's why the majority did not exercise this regularly. Those outcomes are in agreement by means of numerous additional researches that are completed all over the world. Amid a variety of reasons not practicing rubber dam, solitary regular answer was lack of exercise as 43% of individuals felt that they did not have enough exercise for rubber dam usage throughout

undergraduate medical classes (Table 3). This fault was more uncovered by 66% of individuals; they think rubber dam was quite hard to put in room. 89% thinks that it was time wasting (Table 3). One solution for this is that students should need to practice rubber dam pre medical and medical classes on regular basis, problems will be the ease down hence as a result time of request shortens. This is quite clear that if students are up to date with functioning method, rubber dam processes can be done in five minutes. It is in fact the Dentist not have of skills owing to which he does not like rubber dam as compared to not have enough exercise.

Concerning patients' first choice to let a working dentist to toil below rubber dam separation, 58% dentists did not put rubber dams for the reason that of patients' fright or dissimilarity. You can find research studies which disagree with those results and disclose patients' first choice to experience dental cure under rubber dam separation. Research completed in the region of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa on the problem proves that if profit of rubber dam is told to the patients, their dread for its position decreases. Mostly, patients' support is needed if the dentist is certain with effectiveness and worth of rubber dam. It is seen that one experienced dentist creates fewer anxiety in position of rubber dam. Dentists may use up desirable point in time to clarify the consequence, security and efficiency of rubber dam in transportation out healing actions.

Bulks (40%) of individuals in this study opinion poll were last year dental students. Those students immediately following after completing their last specialized assessment were given interim permit from Pakistan Medical and Dental Council to perform common dentistry therefore; they were incorporated in this research. It is a common saying they are in their medical practice perform whatsoever they have studied throughout undergraduate medical schooling and proof shows to separation of operational ground by means of rubber dam is not extremely accepted technique in use.

Review researches contain a few inherent issues. For example, participants might not similar to offer exact, truthful reply or he might sense worried to give reply, which can place them in adverse circumstances. Recent research also faces the same flaw, as we are not confident how precise these findings of rubber dam are. As a result, it suggested that medical students alongside interneers would be necessary to practice rubber dam earlier than initial healing practice. Active dentists, in continuing dental education (CDE) programs, seminars and hands-on

workshops are required to conduct to create awareness and profits of rubber dam and to get better their physical deftness to put this faster. It clearly, will make sure salvage of excellence dental handling to the patients. Limitations of the research comprise that institutions were not chosen and some last year student, interneers or teachers concerned in common dental working who freely fill the survey form was incorporated in this research.

CONCLUSION:

This research shows that dentists might have been students, interneers or graduate dentists functioning in Lahore. Do not exploit uses of rubber dam for a variety of reasons. Lack in exercise consequences in much time taking and hard process. Among the doctors, a very positive reply of 81% revealed that a very high percentage (76%) of Medical Students, interneers and Dental Doctors working in Lahore teaching Hospitals paid no attention to rubber dam placement in their routine job. Uout of 100% 89% of Doctors who were not interested in using it because they thought it as a time wasting, while others 66% found it heavy due to which it was very hard to put it. Few other reasons due to which people shun to use rubber dam are that 50% participants thinks the regular tearing pages and patient's fright approach towards rubber dam.

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